

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

IMPACT OF EROSION PROCESS ON AGROCHEMICAL AND AGROPHYSICAL INDICATORS OF PODZOL-YELLOW-CLAYEY SOILS IN THE LANKARAN ZONE OF AZERBAIJAN

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ABSTRACT

Issues of soil degradation in the Lankaran natural-economic zone possessing a great economical potential for the agricultural development in Azerbaijan have been looked over in the article. Firstly, the information about plant, soil cover, climate, relief and geological structure, hydrological characters and other parameters of the natural condition of the investigated zone was collected and analyzed. Strong decrease of fertility parameters and genetic peculiarities of the tea plant significantly increases productivity search soils as a result of the erosion process was noted. Change of the irrigated-yellow-gleyey soils under the influence of anthropogenic effect was also learnt in the article. The irrigated yellow-gleyey soils are widely used in agriculture. Their most part is used under tea, citrus and vegetable plants. The morphological structure of these soils has changed as a result of irrigation, they differ from virgin versions. But illuvial "B" layer of soil differs with its claying and very hard cloddy structure. Presence of clayey layer on the "B"- "BC" layers is very characteristic for yellow-clayey soils. A level of underground soil is close to 0,5-1 m. Leaching and accumulation of easily soluble salts is directly related to the level of soil cultivation. General characteristic is high humidity in autumn-winter, but prolonged aridity in summer. Prolonged rains in autumn-winter, but aridity and enough heat in summer formed special hydrothermal regime of soil formation. The highest yield growth was in the version with (average in 4-years) N_{250} (ammonia sulphate) $P_{150}K_{120} + 30$ tons of compost. (3480 kg/h or 207,0%). Application $N_{250}P_{150}K_{120} + 30$ tons of compost per hectare under tea plant significantly increases productivity and quality of the yield. The most rational version was applied in 9,0 hectares of tea plantation in the Green Tea farms and Lankaran tea subsidiary (1,0 h).

Keywords: Lankaran zone of Azerbaijan, tea plant, Gleyic Livosols, erosive processes, agrophysical parameters, agrochemical character of soils, depth of groundwater, anthropogenic soils, productivity.

INTRODUCTION

Protection, stable development and usage of natural resources are global problem of the XXI century. The farmer farms should be well acquainted with the peculiarities of their soils, improve the degraded soils, scientifically determine the usage methods. The Lankaran-Astara region was busy with an ancient agriculture and intensively used zones at present. The plants grown in the podzol-gleyey-yellow soils. especially agrotechnical measures in the tea soils, including fertilization and irrigation systems weren't correctly followed and that's why they exposed to chemical, physical-chemical and biological degradation.

Here, a quick development of the anthropogenic degradation process is very dangerous for ownership form, farmer agriculture. From this point of view, regulation of plant, water and nourishment regimes in the soils exposed to degradation is considered one of the most urgent issues.

The large state programs are fulfilling in the ecological field, as in different areas in our country. The President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Mr. Ilham Aliyev said in connection with the holding of the 29th session of the Conference of the Parties to the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change – COP 29 in 2024

in our country: "Azerbaijan systematically supports the global fight against climate change and takes action in connection with energy efficiency. Clean environment and green development are our national priorities. 2024 was declared the year of Green world solidarity in Azerbaijan". The continuous use of the soil and plant diversity, their protection are considered one of the most urgent problems. Recently, the landscape complexes and soil cover are regularly exposing to ecological changes as a result of anthropogenic factors. The soils of the zone are gleyey-yellow, they differ with their poor acid reaction, absence of calcareous of profile and etc. The soils with such indicators give a chance to grow citrus, river and other subtropical plants. But, the investigated soils possess some negative peculiarities in the condition with surplus humidity. One of such characters is presence "B" molded clay layer spreading at a depth from 40-50 cm to 100-150cm, this layer have inconvenient physical-chemical peculiarities. The inconvenient water-air regime, physical-mechanical indicators, heavy clayey and surplus moisture are main factors which prevent normal development of the citrus and tea plants. Therefore, comparative study of agrochemical characters along with water-physical peculiar-

ities of gleyey-yellow soils having unsatisfactory indications is one of the most important issues in order to plant crops [8,15,16]. Closeness of underground water to surface along with prolonged and mostly incorrect cultivation and development gleying process strongly decreased agronomical value of these soils. The temperature systematically rises beginning from early spring to summer, but strongly reduces in autumn in the podzol-gleyey-yellow soils of the research zone. Especially, strong humidity (in December-January) and severe aridity of soil in summer indicate its negative effect very much, it strongly changed ecological fertility parameters depending on seasons. So, recently it was determined that the soil fertility strongly decreases and soil cover degrades and the desertification process intensifies as a result of the human's incorrect farming activity.

OBJECT AND METHODS OF THE RESEARCH

The researches were performed in the experimental-research areas selected in Lankaran in 2021-2024. The experiments were performed in foothill and plain areas of the Lankaran-Astara region, in the Lankaran Tea branch and Hirkan farming zones of the Azerbaijan Fruit-growing and Tea-growing Scientific-Research Institute. Non-eroded and averagely washed podzol-gleyey-yellow soils (in WRB Gleyic Livosols) of the Lankaran-Astara region were selected as a research object. A main aim of the research is to investigate measures system of the agrochemical and agrophysical character of gleyey-yellow soils under tea plant which widespread in the Lankaran-Astara zone and are intensively used in agricultural production and work out measures system for fertility improvement. The following principles are taken as a basis: complex investigation (natural-historical condition of soil type, main indicators and rational use of fertility, agroecological assessment); comparatively investigation (comparison of agrophysical-agrochemical indices and ecological control in non-degraded and averagely degraded soils); economical investigation (economical rationality of use from soil area).

The research method was referred to the methodical recommendations worked out in 70-80 years of the last years and V.R.Volobuyev [1953], G.Sh.Mammadov [1992], S.Z. Mammadova [2005] and other researchers' methods. The work was fulfilled in three stages: field works, laboratorial and generalized works. The following work was realized in the field experiments: the soil temperature was measured by Savvinov thermometer, the field humidity by weight method (it was dried at 105 °C for 5 hours) in thermostat and a bulky weight of soil was calculated for Vasilyev cylinder. For this purpose, the soil sections more than 20 were applied in the different depths of the characteristic places in the research zone, the samples were taken on genetic layers and laboratorial analyses were performed. The GPS coordinates of each soil section were registered and used in researches. M.P.Babayev and E.A.Gurbanov's methods (2008) were used in evaluation of degradation degrees. The chemical analysis and mathematical methods were used for generally accepted method. Exactness of the obtained results in

cameral works (mathematical calculation of the crop and information indications) were performed mathematical-dispersion analysis (B.A.Dospekhov, 1978.; E.A.Dimitriyev 2009), the correlative relations among the indications were fulfilled in Excel 2007 program.

The experiments were performed on the following schemes with 5 versions, 3 repetitions, 100 m² area of each section: **non-eroded soils**: 1) Control (without fertilizer); 2) P₁₅₀K¹²⁰+20 t/h compost (background); 3) background +N₁₀₀; 4) Background +N₁₈₀, 5) Background +N₂₅₀; **Averagely eroded soil**: 1) Control (without fertilizer); 2) P₁₅₀K₁₂₀+30 t/h compost (background); 3) background +N₁₀₀ 4) background +N₁₈₀ 5) background +N₂₅₀.

Mineral fertilizer were used in the experiment: ammonium-sulfate (affected nitrogen 21%); Superphosphate (affected phosphorus 18%), potassium sulfate (affected potassium 46%). Components of "Lankaran" compost: 50% manure, 26% remnants of the vegetable and tea plants, 10% bird manure, 8% wastes of the tea and vegetable industry, 4% acidifying (by adding 2% simple superphosphate and ammonium sulfate) substances; Chemical composition of compost: nitrogen-1,50%, phosphorus-0,80%; potassium -1,85%, organic substance -25%.

DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS

Incorrect use from fertilization and irrigation system decreased potential and effective fertility of these soils for a long time. Up to now, comparative study of agro-physical and agro-chemical characters of different degradation kinds of the tea podzol-gleyey-yellow soils was the center of attention, but it wasn't sufficiently learnt depending on soil complexity.

A quantity of total humus in the samples taken to study the agro-chemical characters of the soil and its factual initial quantity vibrated by 0,85-1,60% at 0-100cm layer. It was potentially determined that total nitrogen is 0,07-0,13% at 0-100 cm (0-30, 30-60, 60-100 cm), total phosphorus -0,05-0,12%, total potassium-0,60-2,10%. An amount of nutrients in the soil which easily assimilated by the plant: absorbed ammoniac is 6,50-10,65 mg/kg, easily hydrolyzed nitrogen is 28-85 mg/kg, nitrate nitrogen is 2,4-6,3 mg/kg, gross phosphorus-9,15-24,35 mg/kg, exchangeable potassium -108-140 mg/kg at 0-100 cm of the soil layer. The soil with neutral pH-index, or weak and moderate degree of acid reaction can be selected for citrus plants. According to the adopted gradation in the Republic (A.N.Gulamadov, F.H.Akhundov, S.Z.Ibrahimov-1980), the podzol-clayey-yellow soils are poorly provided with nutrients. An amount of the same elements on the upper layer of the averagely washed soils is little [9, 10, 13, 14] compared to unwashed soils. Therefore, application of organic, mineral fertilizers is necessary to get high, qualitative yield from tea plant and restore natural fertility of soil. A quantity of total humus, total NPK and nutrients easily assimilated by the plant at 1cm layer of soil in the basic development phases of the vegetation period have been studied for years. As it is seen from Table 1, an amount of gross forms of nutrients increased under the influence of fertilizers in the research years (Table-1). On average a quantity of total humus vibrates on 1,3-2,9% at 1m layer of the non-

degraded tea soils for 4 years. Total nitrogen is 0,10-0,16 %, total phosphorus -0,13-0,18 %, potassium-2,65-2,54 %, they belong to potential fertility on profile in these soils. Ammoniac dissolved in water is 5,8-12,5 , absorbed ammoniac-31,6-61,4, nitrate nitrogen -1,5-5,4 mg/kg, gross phosphorus -98,0-113,0 mg/kg, exchangeable potassium – 115,0-170,0 mg/kg in 1 kg of soil.

According to the performed laboratorial and field researches we can come to such conclusion that physical-chemical, water-physical characters of soil improve, a quantity of gross nutrients rises under the influence of organic and mineral fertilizers in soil profile (Table-1) as a result of coagulation of dispersion particles and exchangeable reaction in averagely degraded soils.

Table 1
Agro-chemical character of the soils in the experimental area (on average in 4-years - 2021-2024) Non-degraded soils (moderately degraded soils)

Depth, cm	Humus, %	Total nitrogen, %	Nitrogen			Phosphorus		Potassium		Ph- water	Ph- salt
			Absorbed N/NH ₃ , mg/kg	Dissolved N/NH ₃ , mg/kg	N/NO ₃ , mg/kg	Total phosphorus, %	Gross (P ₂ O ₅), mg/kg	Total, %	Exchangeable, mg/kg		
<i>Non-degraded soils</i>											
0-30	2,9	0,16	61,4	12,5	5,4	0,18	113,0	2,54	170,0	5,5	4,6
30-60	2,4	0,12	50,8	10,8	3,8	0,15	114,6	2,28	136,0	5,4	4,6
60-100	1,3	0,10	31,6	5,8	1,5	0,13	98,0	2,65	115,0	5,6	4,7
<i>moderately degraded soils</i>											
0-30	1,6	0,08	23,6	7,3	3,2	0,11	72,5	1,55	93,0	5,5	4,2
30-60	1,5	0,06	14,7	5,4	2,8	0,11	34,7	1,57	65,0	6,4	4,0
60-100	1,0	0,05	10,8	4,2	1,6	0,10	24,5	1,43	63,0	6,0	4,5

Table2
Agro-physical character of podzol-clayey-yellow soils (on average in 4-years 2021-2024) Non-degraded soils (moderately degraded soils)

Section №	Depth, cm	Bulky weight, g/cm before cultivation	Bulky weight, g/cm ³	Special weight, g/cm ³	Porosity, %
<i>Non-degraded soils</i>					
1	0-30	1,28	1,25	2,45	51,0
	30-60	1,44	1,23	2,54	49,0
	60-100	1,37	1,26	2,63	47,0
<i>moderately degraded soils</i>					
2	0-30	1,47	1,33	2,68	49,5
	30-60	1,36	1,30	2,73	48,7
	60-100	1,49	1,48	2,80	48,6

This is 1,37-1,28 g/cm³ in non-degraded soils and 1,47-1,49 g/cm³ in averagely degraded soils at 0-30 cm layer before agro-cultivated soils under tea plant. The bulky weight rises towards the lower layers. This increase is clearly shown in “B” layer. So, sometimes the bulky weight vibrates by 1,33-1,48 g/cm³ at 0,6-1 m depth layer in non-degraded and moderately degraded soils under tea plant. It is seen from experiments that

the porosity decreased 1,5 %, but the bulky mass increased 0,05 g/cm³ in the sowing layer (0-30 cm) of the moderately degraded soils compared to degraded soils. When the structure of fertile soils is higher, the degradation process is poor there.

The water-physical porosity and structure of soil are closely related to its fertility. The erosion and sliding processes intensify as a result of deterioration of these indicators [12]. Destruction of the structure under

the influence of natural factors or bad cultivation of soil reduces total porosity. Application of organic fertilizers mostly affects its porosity [3]. The soil structure, porosity is strongly disturbed as a result of decrease of humus, organic remnants in the degraded soils. The atmospheric waters can't soak, much water loss occurs, the plants suffer from drought in such condition. As a rule, the moisture is lack in the degraded soils. As a result, the plants can't use the nutrients in composition of soil and applied fertilizers in the soil that lacks moisture [4]. Our experimental versions in some objects of degraded clayey-yellow soils indicated that application of different mechanical, physical-chemical, biological and hydro-technical methods is important in increase of fertility efficiency of soils. This circumstance in moderately degraded soils is explained that the surplus water which remained on the soil surface can't intensively soak in soil. That's why clayey layer between "B" and "C" layers is deeply softened with different softeners.

Some researchers [1, 2] widely explained rationality of application of nitrogen fertilizers in the tea plantations with their experiments according to the research direction. It was determined that ammonium nitrogen is weakly absorbed in very surplus humid yellow-podzol soils. Though the absorbing coefficient of nitrogen is higher than phosphorus and potassium, this index isn't

more than 40-50%. However, the fertilizers with ammonium can be leached to a depth of 15-20 cm from the place of application [5, 11]. But washing of ammonium nitrogen is weaker in comparison with nitrate nitrogen. So, nitrate nitrogen is more at 0-16 m layer of these soils and it gradually rises in July, August and relatively decreases in September, October and moves to the deep layers (20-50 cm). Ammoniac nitrogen decreases from the beginning to the end of vegetation [4]. Special experiments have been performed to study separate application dose of nitrogen fertilizers and their ratio to each other. For this purpose, the stationary experiments were applied to use norms and ratios of the different kinds of mineral and organic fertilizers depending on nitrogen fertilizer norms and improvement of the tea soil fertility in Lankaran Tea Experimental Farm of the Azerbaijan Scientific –Research Institute of Fruit-growing and Tea-growing in 2021-2024. Application of ammonium fertilizer forms of nitrogen in plants was considered necessary to intensify nourishment of the plants with nitrogen in the degraded soils. During the experiment, application of PK+20 tons of "Lankaran" compost (in background) in nitrogen fertilizer affects well its root system and leaf apparatus and was a reason for obtaining of high green tea leaf (Table 3).

Table 3

Impact of different nitrogen forms on productivity of the green tea leaf (Hirkan settlement, non-degraded podzol-clayey-yellow soils)

№	Variants	Productivity (4 year average)		
		Productivity, kg/ha	Growth, ha	
			kg	%
1	Control (no fertilizer)	1680	-	-
2	P ₁₅₀ K ₁₂₀ +20t/ha compost (background)	3230	1550	92,3
3	background+N ₁₀₀	3820	2140	167,0
4	background+N ₁₈₀	4480	2800	127,4
5	background+N ₂₅₀	5160	3480	207,0

It is seen from Table 4 that this indicator slightly increased (1870 kg/h) in the "Lankaran" compost (background) variant with PK+30 tons, if the crop amount was 1060 kg/h in the control version of moderately degraded soil without fertilizer (1870 kg/h). The highest yield was obtained in the variant with background +N₂₅₀ among the versions with the separate nitrogen fertilizer doses. So, the best result was in the var-

iant with background +N₂₅₀, 3700 kg of yield was obtained from a hectare, and it means an increase of 2640kg or 249.0 % compared to the non-fertilized control option. Increase of productivity in the variant with 250 kg nitrogen is 3480 kg or 20,7% compared to control option while an annual norm of nitrogen increased from 100 kg to 250 kg in the non-degraded podzol-clayey-yellow soils of the Hirkan settlement.

Table 4.

Influence of nitrogen fertilizers with different norms on productivity of the green tea leaves (moderately degraded soils, Lankaran Tea branch)

№	Variants	Productivity (4 year average)		
		Productivity, kg/ha	Growth, ha	
			kg	%
1	Control (no fertilizer)	1060	-	-
2	P ₁₅₀ K ₁₂₀ +30 t/ha compost (background)	1870	810	76,4
3	background +N ₁₀₀	2730	1670	157,5
4	background +N ₁₈₀	3620	2560	241,5
5	background +N ₂₅₀	3700	2640	249,0

But it is necessary to note that an efficiency of nitrogen fertilizers applied in different doses is various depending on degrading degree of soils. The 4-year researches indicate that an annual norm of nitrogen (in phosphorus and potassium background) the moderately degraded podzol-yellow –clayey soils were provided with nutrients as a result of denitrification and washing, the highest additional yield was obtained when an annual norm of nitrogen (in phosphorus and potassium background) is increased from 100 kg to 250 kg and 250 kg of nitrogen fertilizer is applied per hectare. Application of background +N₂₅₀ of fertilizers in the area with moderately washed soil increased the productivity of the green tea leaf 2 times compared to the area without fertilization. It should be noted that the crop obtained from fertilized area was equal to the yield in the area with unfertilized and unwashed soil. So, while applying 250 kg of nitrogen per hectare, the yield of the green tea leaf is 2640 kg (249,0 %) in comparison with the control and 970 kg more than the variant with 100 kg of nitrogen (Table 4).

Lack of nitrogen, one of the nutrients necessary for plant development is reason for decrease in productivity. The plants absorb 50 % of nitrogen in the soil. 25

% of nitrogen evaporates in gaseous form as a result of denitrification. The rest parts are washed and mix with underground and surface waters. So, application of 250 kg nitrogen in 1 hectare of old tea plantations in podzol-clayey-yellow soils of the Lankaran-Astara region significantly increases productivity and quality of green tea leaf yield. The qualitative indicators of the tea plant also have a great importance along with its productivity [6, 7]. Nitrogen fertilizer increases productivity of tea plant and improves its quality. The taste, aroma, etc. of a low-quality product is low. During the period when nitrogen was applied against the background of ammonium-sulphate, phosphorus and potassium from fertilizer forms, the calculated dose (N₂₅₀) in the given options (Table 5).

From 4-year researches in the podzol-clayey-yellow soils it was determined that the qualitative indicators of the crop were in the version with the background+N₂₅₀ along with the highest productivity of the green tea leaf in the non-degraded and moderately degraded soils. It can be clearly seen in the variants without fertilizer in the moderately degraded soils and in the variants with mineral fertilizers (Table 5).

Table 5

Effect of nitrogen fertilizer applied in different norm on the quality of green tea leaf yield. In 4 years moderate. (Non-degraded soils)

№	Variants	Tannin	Extractives
1	Control (no fertilizer)	20,3	35,2
2	P ₁₅₀ K ₁₂₀ +30 t/ha compost (background)	22,7	37,0
3	background +N ₁₀₀	23,4	38,5
4	background +N ₁₈₀	23,5	43,6
5	background +N ₂₅₀	23,7	43,8

It is recommended to apply an effective fertilizer dose of 260 kg/h to old tea plantations and 180 kg/h ton young plantations. The researches show that the combined supply of nitrogen to tea plantations against the background of organic and mineral fertilizers increases the cold resistance and productivity of the plant. The general development of the tea plants is provided, productivity increases while applying 30-40 tons of manure, nitrogen at the expense of 180 -250 kg of active substance and 150 kg of phosphorus, 120 kg of potassium per hectare every 2-3 years. It is considered appropriate to give N₂₅₀ kg of nitrogen per hectare in podzol-clayey-yellow soils with mechanical content, heavy granules, and less clay, and N₁₈₀ kg per hectare in relatively clayey-sandy shales and sandy soils. On the basis of the experiments it was determined that 180-250 kg of nitrogen should be applied per hectare while a width and length of 18-20 old bushes is 80-100 x 100-120 cm.

CONCLUSION

We can come to such conclusion from the performed 4-year researches:

The productivity of plants reduces and crop quality decreases because the nutrients in the eroded podzol-clayey-yellow soils are washed. Therefore the application of mineral and organic fertilizers together is of great importance in order to restore fertility of

washed podzol-clayey-yellow soils and increase plant productivity and quality.

If an amount of the yield was 1060 kg/h in the control variant of moderately degraded soils in the Lankaran tea branch, this index slightly increased (1870 kg/h) in the variant of PK+30 tons “Lankaran” (background) compost. The best result among the increase norms of nitrogen was got 3700 kg yield from each hectare in the variant of background +N₂₅₀, this means an increase of 2640 kg or 249,0 % compared to the control option without fertilizer.

Increase is 3480 kg or 20,7 % compared to the control variant with nitrogen productivity of 250 kg while increasing the annual norm from 100 kg to 250 kg per hectare in the non-degraded podzol-gleyey-yellow soils of the Hirkan settlement. It is advisable to give nitrogen fertilizers in the form of ammonium sulphate in weakly acidic soils with yellow-podzol spread in the Lankaran zone, where there is a lot of precipitation. So, 30 kg of nitrate nitrogen is washed from each hectare under an influence of precipitations in these soils. Application of nitrogen fertilizers with nitrate to the tea soils in the terrace sowings isn't good. On the other hand tea plantations grown on podzol –yellow and podzol-gleyey-yellow and other types of yellow soils, which constitute the main soil fund of Lankaran region,

develop better especially on acidic and weakly acidic soils (pH 4,5-6,5). Therefore, it is very convenient to give physiological acid fertilizers to the soil under the river.

Giving nitrogen fertilizer and ammonium sulphate fertilizer to tea bushes significantly increases the growth and development of the plant as well as its productivity. The effective dose of fertilizer for old tea plantations is 260 kg/h, and for young plantations 180 kg application is recommended.

Rational results of the research were applied in 30 hectares of tea plantations

The effective results of the research were applied to 30 h of tea plantations in a large area in Lankaran tea branch and "Green Tea" farms.

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